

TRANSFER OF MEANING IN HADITH TEXTS

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Annotation . This in the article Islam is sacred source calculated hadith texts linguistic the point from the point of view analysis mainly hadith in the texts meaning move to the event attention is directed .

Key words : hadith texts , meaning and his development , meaning change, metaphor , cognitive linguistics , cognitive meaning

Ever since of linguistics the most important , central problematic issues one meaning and his development is the issue . Linguistics the most ancient from periods right from the start meaning and him its representative is linguistic unity between attitude nature about debate continuous continue reached will come . Language development stage , mainly formal on the side changes observed such as language of unity meaning - content on the side surface coming changes are also known . Separately to emphasize OK , language of units meaning - content on the side face giving changes of the tongue shaped level face giving from changes more extensive and is faster . That is this in progress language of the owner needs , aspirations , to the world relationship solution doer role plays , that is language of the owner cognitive activity management task passes because cognitive of activity on the ground exactly meaning lies. Har how language his own the owner with together with the owner mental , social and cultural perfect with in harmony goes like this language of the owner to the national mental self characteristics solution doer role plays. In the language meaning development whole language development own from the points is one Already researchers separately as they noted , " linguistic meanings development of the universe fate , interests , nature , traditions , beliefs , thinking style each how from chronicles according to better reflection " .

A metaphor a person cognitive activity , perception power up powerful one of the weapons as mental and linguistically processes to action brings. Highlight It should be a metaphor event from long ago the world philology in science research reached bride although it is an art from the framework , stylistics , rhetoric from within out not issued . More precisely , the past of the century to their heads until metaphor science , science language , terminology lie down event as interpretation reach priority by doing will come . Basically , antique philosophers metaphor of speech decoration , speech grass , artistry tool interpretation what they did known . English rationalist philosophers speech , eng first of all , the idea to express and get educated transmission for service it does task perform for only right in a sense applied only words those who consider it valid . Even T. Hobbes " Lost " metaphor He calls them " fires " . and of them use " innumerable nonsense between with " to tempt " . equal to that emphasizes (this of expressions that it exists in itself not noticing possible it's not !). Such think near in view was of philosophers most of them scientific in the

works metaphor to use road put that it won't be they say and a metaphor to apply to crime they equalize . To romanticism inclined philosopher and scientists and , on the contrary , a metaphor thought only of expression not but thinking is also unique those who know it as a method . For example , German philosopher F. Nietzsche , in general , know essence metaphorical that emphasizes .

20th century come , especially in later times cognitive of linguistics formation with to the metaphor to look Entirely changed , his scope expanded .

Metaphors in hadith texts as well applied they are more. Our Prophet sav and companions in his speech occurs . It is known , Rasulullah sav . one of the first preachers of Islam considered , first of all , himself to everyone example to be must was. That's why it 's amazing behaviors and spoke speeches beautiful , fluent and clear , impressive was : Muaz ibn Jabal God willing anhudan narrative will be : " Clothes worn out As torn , the Qur'an is also some nations in the heart wears out ..." (Quran healing of souls , p. 273, from Dorimiy). This in the text applied " *The Qur'an is also some nations in the heart becomes obsolete*" in the sentence in metaphor content similarity is available .

Jubayr ibn Mut'im God willing anhudan narrative will be : " Nabi peace be upon him alayhi vassal evening Surah "Tour" in prayer what they are reading i heard He said, " Maybe they are never from the thing injured maybe the rest or they are themselves creators ?! Maybe the heavens and they also the earth did they create ? - No , they are do not believe " - to the verse arrived when they come , my heart flying to go little left " (Quran hearts healing , 287). This " *My heart* " in the hadith *flying to go little left* " Jubayr in the combination ra by Quran meanings deep realize enough himself light nice that he did wants to emphasize will be and this in metaphor being , in this substantive likeness surface came out

Above thoughts and from samples so to the conclusion our arrival it is possible , therefore , a hadith in the texts meaning move phenomenon occurs and this hadith to the texts to himself typical meaning to be expressed service does. Also hadith in the texts occurring grass type as a metaphor more speaker speech impressive let it come out provided.

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